

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, Chapter 1.

Figure 1.2 Timeline of key strategic events and advances in the understanding of biological invasions

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Project leader and contributors:

- Helen Roy (hele@ceh.ac.uk)
- Joana S. Vicente
- Tatsiana Lipinskaya
- Daniel Simberloff
- Tanara Renard Truong
- Ankila Hiremath
- Llewellyn Foxcroft
- Sankaran Kavileveetil
- Morelia Camacho-Cervantes
- Melodie McGeoch
- Lora Peacock
- Betty Rono

Data curator:

- Tanara Renard Truong

Description

This figure presents a timeline of key strategic events and advances in the understanding of biological invasions. It shows milestone events relevant to biological invasions, major publications on biological invasions, examples of invasive alien species' first record, and examples of successful management, with the central line graph (orange) illustrating the global escalation in first records of alien species.

Process overview

Following an internal consultation, the co-chairs decided to focus on 5 kinds of information: a) trends of the first records of alien species, b) examples of introductions, c) examples of successful management, d) major events and e) major publications on biological invasions. Collection of evidence was conducted through surveys among the expert group and literature reviews. Examples (introduction and management) were selected to ensure balance among taxa and regions.

Protocol for the collection of evidence

- a. **Graph (central line):** adapted from Seebens, Blackburn, et al. (2017)

Seebens, H., Blackburn, T. M., Dyer, E. E., Genovesi, P., Hulme, P. E., Jeschke, J. M., Pagad, S., Pyšek, P., Winter, M., Arianoutsou, M., Bacher, S., Blasius, B., Brundu, G., Capinha, C., Celesti-Grapow, L., Dawson, W., Dullinger, S., Fuentes, N., Jäger, H., ... Essl, F. (2017). No saturation in the accumulation of alien species worldwide. *Nature Communications*, 8(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14435>

b. Examples of introduction: examples selected from the list of species found by a literature review conducted as part of Chapter 1 (see 10.5281/zenodo.5518255).

The selection criteria were:

- taxonomic balance
- regional balance
- balance among realms (freshwater, marine and terrestrial)

<i>Magallana angulata</i> (Portuguese oyster) was introduced in Europe in the 1500s	Edwards, C. "A study in erratic distribution: the occurrence of the medusa <i>Gonionemus</i> in relation to the distribution of oysters." <i>Advances in Marine Biology</i> . Vol. 14. Academic Press, 1977. 251-284.
<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i> (rabbits) was first recorded in Australia in 1859	Fenner, F. (2010). Deliberate introduction of the European rabbit, <i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i> , into Australia. <i>Revue scientifique et technique</i> , 29(1), 103.
<i>Acacia dealbata</i> (acacia bernier) was first recorded in Sri Lanka in 1870	Midgley, S. J., & Vivekanandan, K. (1987). Australian acacias in Sri Lanka. <i>ACIAR Proceedings, Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research</i> , 132-135.
<i>Pondetaria crassipes</i> (water hyacinth) was first recorded in North America in 1884	Klorer, J. (1909). <i>The water hyacinth problem. Journal of the Association of Engineering Societies</i> , 42, 42-48.
<i>Leiothrix lutea</i> (red-billed leiothrix) was first introduced in Europe in the late 1800s	Pereira, P. F., Barbosa, A. M., Godinho, C., Salgueiro, P. A., Silva, R. R., & Lourenço, R. (2020). The spread of the red-billed leiothrix (<i>Leiothrix lutea</i>) in Europe: The conquest by an overlooked invader?. <i>Biological Invasions</i> , 22(2), 709-722.
<i>Rhinella marina</i> (cane toad) was first recorded in Australia in 1935	Shine, R., Ward-Fear, G., & Brown, G. P. (2020). A famous failure: Why were cane toads an ineffective biocontrol in Australia?. <i>Conservation Science and Practice</i> , 2(12), e296.
<i>Boiga irregularis</i> (brown tree snake) was first recorded in Guam in the late 1940s or early 1950s	Savidge, J. A. (1988). Food habits of <i>Boiga irregularis</i> , an introduced predator on Guam. <i>Journal of Herpetology</i> , 275-282.
<i>Lates niloticus</i> (Nile perch) was first recorded in Lake Victoria in 1954	Goudswaard, K. P., Witte, F., & Katunzi, E. F. (2008). The invasion of an introduced predator, Nile perch (<i>Lates niloticus</i> , L.) in Lake Victoria (East Africa): chronology and

	causes. <i>Environmental Biology of Fishes</i> , 81(2), 127-139.
<i>Dreissena polymorpha</i> (zebra mussel) was first recorded in North American Great Lakes in 1986	Carlton, J. T. (2008). The zebra mussel <i>Dreissena polymorpha</i> found in North America in 1986 and 1987. <i>Journal of Great Lakes Research</i> , 34(4), 770-773.
<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i> (sea walnut) was first recorded in the Black Sea in 1982	Carlton, J. T. (2008). The zebra mussel <i>Dreissena polymorpha</i> found in North America in 1986 and 1987. <i>Journal of Great Lakes Research</i> , 34(4), 770-773.

c. Examples of management: a call for examples was circulated among the expert group. The selection was essentially based on consensus and regional balance.

Control of <i>Opuntia monacantha</i> (common prickly pear) in South Africa (1913) and Australia (1914)	Van Wilgen, B.W., Moran, V.C. and Hoffmann, J.H., 2013. Some perspectives on the risks and benefits of biological control of invasive alien plants in the management of natural ecosystems. <i>Environmental Management</i> , 52(3), pp.531-540.
Eradication of <i>Ondatra zibethicus</i> (muskrat) in the United Kingdom in 1939	Gosling, L.M. and Baker, S.J., 1989. The eradication of muskrats and coypus from Britain. <i>Biological Journal of the Linnean Society</i> , 38(1), pp.39-51.
<i>Anopheles gambiae</i> (African malaria mosquito) was successfully managed in Brazil in the 1930s and early 1940s	Killeen, G.F., Fillinger, U., Kiche, I., Gouagna, L.C. and Knols, B.G., 2002. <i>Eradication of Anopheles gambiae from Brazil: lessons for malaria control in Africa?</i> . <i>The Lancet infectious diseases</i> , 2(10), pp.618-627.
Control of <i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i> (rabbits) in Australia in 1955	Henzell, R.P., Cooke, B.D. and Mutze, G.J., 2008. The future biological control of pest populations of European rabbits, <i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i> . <i>Wildlife Research</i> , 35(7), pp.633-650.
Rinderpest is first wild animal disease to be eliminated globally in 2011	Rinderpest is first wild animal disease to be eliminated globally in 2011 Morens, D.M., Holmes, E.C., Davis, A.S. and Taubenberger, J.K., 2011. Global rinderpest eradication: lessons learned and why humans should celebrate too. <i>Journal of Infectious Diseases</i> , 204(4), pp.502-505.

d. Milestone events: A first timeline was adapted from Simberloff (2013). It was refined after the external reviews of the first and second order draft.

Simberloff, D. (2013). *Invasive species: what everyone needs to know*. Oxford University Press.

Charles Darwin observed two European plants invading the pampas, Patagonia (1833-1836)
International Convention on Measures to be taken against <i>Phylloxera vastatrix</i> (1881)
Creation of the Office International des Epizooties (OIE) in 1924
African Convention on the Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources: Article 7(5) (1933)
Adoption of the International Plant Protection Convention (IPPC) in 1951
Launch of the Scientific Committee on Problems of the Environment (SCOPE) programme on the Ecology of Biological Invasions in 1982
Adoption of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) in 1982
Opening for signature of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), including Article 8(h) on alien species, in 1992
Creation of the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Invasive Species Specialist Group (ISSG) in 1994
Launch of the Global Invasive Species Programme (GISP) in 1997
Adoption of the CBD Guiding Principles annexed to decision VI/23 on alien species, in 2002
Adoption of the Ballast Water Management Convention in 2004
Adoption by the CBD of the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020 (including the Aichi Biodiversity Targets) in 2010
Adoption of the European Union Regulation 1143/2014 on Invasive Alien Species in 2014
Adoption of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, including the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015
Creation of the International Association for Open Knowledge on Invasive Alien Species (INVASIVESNET) in 2017
Adoption of the Arctic Invasive Alien Species (ARIAS) Strategy and Action Plan in 2017
Creation of the Global Register of Introduced and Invasive Species in 2017
Adoption of the Kunming-Montreal Global biodiversity framework in 2022

e. Major publications: a call for examples was circulated among the expert group. The selection was essentially based on consensus and refined after the external reviews of the first and second order draft.

Elton, C. S. (1958). *The Ecology of Invasions by Animals and Plants*. University of Chicago Press.

<http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-1-4899-7214-9>

Hooker, J. D. (1867). *Handbook of the New Zealand flora: A systematic description of the native plants of*

New Zealand and the Chatham, Kermadec's, Lord Auckland's, and Macquarrie's islands (pp. 1–

916). Reeve & Co.,. <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/228754>

IPBES. (2019). *Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services* (p. 1148). IPBES secretariat.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673>

Palmer, T. (1898). The Danger of Introducing Noxious Animals and Birds. *Publications from USDA-ARS / UNL Faculty*. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/usdaarsfacpub/1194>

Wallace, A. R. (1880). *Island life: Or, the phenomena and causes of insular faunas and floras, including a revision and attempted solution of the problem of geological climates*. London: Macmillan & Co.
http://darwin-online.org.uk/converted/Ancillary/1880_IslandLife_S721/1880_IslandLife_S721.html

Wallace, A. R. (1889). *Darwinism: An exposition of the theory of natural selection with some of its applications*. London & New York: Macmillan & Co. <http://darwin-online.org.uk/content/frameset?itemID=A1015&viewtype=text&pageseq=1>

Note: Taxonomy of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF, <https://www.gbif.org/>) and common name of CABI Compendium Invasive Species (<https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/product/qi>) are used for the chapters. Therefore, how species name and/or common name listed in the chapters may differ from the original source of information.